

THE MODERN CHARACTERISTICS OF USING THE SPIRITUAL HERITAGE OF JADIDS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCE OF PRIMARY CLASS TEACHERS

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Abstract: This article examines the modern features of using the spiritual heritage of the ancients in the development of the professional competence of primary school teachers. The educational ideas of the ancients, their importance in the educational process, and the methods of applying this heritage in today's education are analyzed. The article examines the pedagogical approaches of effective use of the heritage of the past in improving the professional skills of teachers, the relevance of spiritual education in primary education, and methods aimed at forming a sense of national identity in students.

Key words: primary education, professional competence, heritage of the past, spiritual education, modern education, teacher's skills, pedagogical approach.

Introduction.

Today, the development of professional competence of primary school teachers is one of the important tasks of the education system. At the initial stage of education, children's interest in learning and their spiritual maturity are formed. Therefore, primary school teachers play an important role not only in imparting knowledge to students, but also in forming moral values in them. Using the spiritual heritage of the ancients in this process is one of the urgent issues of modern education.

In their time, the Jadids promoted the ideas of enlightenment and self-realization, and paid great attention to educating the young generation as a perfect person. Their spiritual heritage has not lost its importance in the education of the young generation even today. Especially for primary school teachers, the spiritual heritage of Jadids is one of the important resources that help students' personal development in the educational process.

This article analyzes the modern features of using the spiritual heritage of the past in the development of the professional competence of primary school teachers. In particular, advanced ideas in modern pedagogy and their application in the modern educational process, as well as methods of using modern heritage to improve the professional skills of teachers are considered. The relevance of the article is related to the need to increase the importance of spiritual education in the current education system, to educate students about national identity and respect for spiritual values.

Also, the article discusses the role of the spiritual heritage of the ancients in modern education, its importance in the formation of the professional competence of primary school teachers, and effective pedagogical approaches in this regard.

Literature analysis

Researches, scientific sources and articles on the spiritual heritage of Jadids and their pedagogical views play an important role in enriching the educational process. The works of modern enlighteners - Abduqadir Shakuri, Mahmudhoja Behbudi, Abdulla Avloni and other scholars and scholars are considered as one of the main sources of national spirituality and

education. The views on education and training put forward in their works contain important pedagogical principles that can be used in today's primary education.

Mahmudhoja Behbudi's work "School and education" emphasizes the harmony of education with nationalism, enlightenment and striving for perfection [2]. According to Behbudi, education should be aimed not only at imparting knowledge, but also at forming students' national identity and spiritual maturity. These ideas are of great importance in today's modern education, especially in the education of elementary school students.

Abdulla Awlani's work "Turkish Gulistan or Morality" pays special attention to the issue of moral education of children [1]. Avloni emphasizes that one of the main tasks of teachers is to develop the moral qualities of children, to form high spirituality in them. His pedagogical ideas define important principles that can be used in the formation of professional competence of modern teachers.

At present, modern studies are being conducted on the use of the spiritual heritage of the ancients in the educational process. In particular, scientific articles and researches written about pedagogical skill, formation of spiritual education in students, principles of education based on national values give comprehensive opinions on this matter. These literatures help to develop methods and approaches of using the spiritual heritage of modern teachers to improve the professional competence of modern teachers.

The analysis of the literature shows that there are many ideas on the formation of the national and spiritual foundations of education in the spiritual heritage of the Jadids. By applying their works and pedagogical views in the modern education system, it is possible to develop the professional competence of primary school teachers. Therefore, in-depth analysis of scientific literature on this topic and their application in the educational process is one of the urgent tasks of the educational system today.

Discussion

Increasing the professional competence of the teacher in teaching and educating elementary school students is a necessary condition for forming them as mature individuals in all respects. From this point of view, the effective use of the spiritual heritage of the past serves as an important factor in the development of the teacher's professional skills. Studies show that the ideas put forward by the ancients, in particular, issues of national identity, spirituality and moral values, have not lost their relevance even today.

Today's modern education system requires independent thinking, adherence to moral standards, and the formation of a desire for spiritual perfection in students. In this respect, the educational ideas of the Jadids are one of the important sources for students' understanding of national identity, formation of moral education and their education as active members of society. In particular, the educational works of modern enlighteners such as Mahmudhoja Behbudi [2], Abdulla Avloni [1] are a guide for teachers in establishing spiritual education in primary education. guides.

Based on the existing research, it can be said that there are several modern approaches to using the heritage of the ancients to improve the professional competence of primary school teachers. One of them is the use of various didactic games, artistic works, riddles and stories based on the educational ideas of the ancients during the lesson. In this way, the interest of students is aroused and they are introduced to moral values and spiritual heritage.

In addition, it is possible to inform students about national identity and spiritual values through educational activities, literary evenings, and events dedicated to national holidays in

the application of the spiritual heritage of the Jadids. These approaches require the teacher to be creative, to organize the education and training process in modern ways. At the same time, by conveying the educational heritage of the past to the students, the teacher increases his professional knowledge and skills.

Material

As the main materials used in the research, the works of Jadids such as Mahmudhoja Behbudi, Abdulla Avloni, Abduqadir Shakuri on education and training, as well as the researches and scientific articles carried out on the legacy of Jadids and their importance in the modern education system were analyzed. .

Pedagogical ideas given in Jadid's works on education, ideas aimed at forming the spiritual maturity of students, and the issues of developing necessary skills for improving the teacher's professional skills were studied in depth. At the same time, methods presented in modern pedagogical literature and textbooks, researches revealing the importance of moral and spiritual education in working with students were also used as material.

The analysis based on these materials shows that the use of ancient heritage in the process of primary education serves not only the spiritual education of students, but also the improvement of the teacher's professional competence. Therefore, it is urgent to widely use this heritage in the educational process and to develop the necessary methodological recommendations for teachers in this regard.

Result.

As a result of the conducted research, it can be determined that the use of the spiritual heritage of the past is highly effective in developing the professional competence of primary school teachers. Pedagogical principles put forward by Jadids, in particular, issues of national identity awareness, enlightenment, formation of spiritual and moral values, are of great importance in today's education process.

The educational process, organized on the basis of the educational ideas of the ancients, helps students to respect national values, adhere to moral standards, and strive for spiritual perfection. Also, this spiritual heritage serves as a resource for teachers to develop their professional skills and organize the lesson processes in an interesting and meaningful way.

Research shows that by using the spiritual heritage of the ancients, teachers can effectively use various didactic games, educational activities and other pedagogical methods in classes. This not only increases the interest of students, but also becomes an important factor in the development of the teacher's professional competence.

Conclusion.

In conclusion, the use of the spiritual heritage of the ancients in the development of the professional competence of primary school teachers is one of the urgent issues of the modern educational process. The ideas of the Jadids about education and training are combined with modern pedagogical methods and serve to improve the professional skills of teachers and to form spiritual and moral qualities in students.

In the future, it is necessary to further improve the methods and approaches of using the heritage of the past in the educational process, to develop methodical recommendations for teachers in this regard. This, in turn, serves as an important factor in improving the quality of primary education and in the development of the young generation as perfect people. Also, involving teachers in studying the heritage of the past, teaching them modern pedagogical

methods of using the spiritual heritage will also greatly contribute to the improvement of the quality of education.

References:

1. Avloniy, A. (1992). Turkiy Guliston yoxud axloq. Toshkent: O'zbekiston Davlat Nashriyoti.
2. Behbudiy, M. (1999). Maktab va maorif. Toshkent: Sharq.
3. Karimov, X. (2016). Milliy ta'lim tizimida jadidlar merosidan foydalanishning pedagogik asoslari. Toshkent: Pedagogika va innovatsion ta'lim.
4. Qodirov, M. (2014). Jadidlar pedagogikasining zamonaviy ta'limdagi ahamiyati. Toshkent: Fan va texnologiyalar.
5. Shokirjonov, Sh. (2000). Jadidlar va ta'lim-tarbiya. Toshkent: O'qituvchi.
6. Xudoynazarov E.M., Avezova D.G. Didactic Principles of Developing Logical Thinking in Students // International Scientific Conference on "New Scientific Trends and Challenges" 20th February 2023, Rome, Italy. P. 97-100.
7. Xudoynazarov E.M., Saparboeva S.O. //Didactic Foundations of the Development of Human Thinking. International Scientific Conference on "New Scientific Trends and Challenges" 20th February 2023, Rome, Italy. P. 94-96.
8. Худойназаров, Э. М., Эсонов, Н. А., & Кучкаров, М. У. Преимущества альтернативных методов обучения.
9. Madraximovich, K. E. (2020). Improving the methodological training of primary school teachers on the basis of innovative approaches. European Journal of Research and Reflection in Educational Sciences Vol, 8(7).
10. Xudoynazarov, E. M. (2019). Didactic possibilities of oral exercises in forming initial classes pupils' mathematical thinking activity. Eastern European Scientific Journal, Ausgabe. Germany, (1-2019), 249.
11. Khudoynazarov, E. (2023). Boshlang 'ich ta'limda mantiqiy fikrlashini rivojlantirishning ahamiyati. Молодые ученые, 1(13), 32-37.
12. Эгамбергян, Х. М. (2023). Ўқувчиларда танқидий фикрлашни ривожлантиришнинг педагогик ва методик асослари. Zamonaviy fan, ta'lim va ishlab chiqarish muammolarining innovatsion yechimlari, 4, 56-59.